

Applications of time-resolved spectroscopy measurements in biological tissues and material (Projekta Nr. LU-BA-PG-2024/1-0031)

Version 1

Description

The Data Management Plan (DMP) is developed in the framework of the Project No 5.2.1.1.i.0/2/24/I/CFLA/007 "Internal and External Consolidation of the University of Latvia" of the second round of the Consolidation and Governance Change Implementation Grants within Investment 5.2.1.1.i "Research, Development and Consolidation Grants" under Reform 5.2.1.r "Higher Education and Science Excellence and Governance Reform" of Reform and Investment Strand 5.2 of the Latvian Recovery and Resilience Mechanism Plan "Ensuring Change in the Governance Model of Higher Education Institutions".

The main goal of this project is to develop a 3D model of light penetration through tissue in the Visible and Near Infrared (520 nm – 800 nm) spectral range based on experimental data. The measurement data of light penetration depth, scattering, absorption, and photon path length will be obtained, analysed, and calculated for pigskin, cow brain, and no biological material. During the project will be published one scientific publication, participate in one conference, and workshop for MSc students within the curriculum.

Funder

European Commission | EC

Grant

Internal and External
Consolidation of the University
of Latvia

(5.2.1.1.i.0/2/24/I/CFLA/007)

Researchers

Vanesa Lukinsone (0000-0003-0065-9561)

Organizations

University of Latvia

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: [Applications of time-resolved spectroscopy measurements in biological tissues and material \(Projekta Nr. LU-BA-PG-2024/1-0031\)](#)

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[Vanessa Lukinsone \(0000-0003-0065-9561\)](#)

Organizations:

[University of Latvia](#)

Contact: [Lukinsone Vanessa \(vanesa.lukinsone@gmail.com\)](mailto:vanesa.lukinsone@gmail.com)

2. Funding

Funding organizations: [European Commission](#) | [EC](#)

Grants: [Internal and External Consolidation of the University of Latvia \(5.2.1.1.i.0/2/24/I/CFLA/007\)](#)

Project: [Applications of time-resolved spectroscopy measurements in biological tissues and material \(Projekta Nr. LU-BA-PG-2024/1-0031\)](#)

3. License

License: CC-BY-4.0

Access Rights: Public

4. Templates

Descriptions

Photon Time-Of-Flight (PTOF)

Photon time-of-flight measurements in the visible and near-infrared spectral range of biological tissues.

Template: LCS FARP

Type: Dataset

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

The photon propagation through biological tissue in the visible spectral range. And calculation scattering and absorption coefficients.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Experimental data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

- CSV
- XLS
- Others

.sdt

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

1

GB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

Other researchers

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

No

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions)

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

Yes

Comment:

Till publication date.

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org/>

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

MS EXCEL SPCImage

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2.4.3 When will the data be made available for re-use?

2025-05-28

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

No

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Vanesa Lukinsone (0000-0003-0065-9561)

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

- Firewall
- Passwords
- Physical access control

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

PTOF Skin

Photon Time-Of-Flight in visible and near-infrared spectral range in skin tissue.

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

The photon propagation through skin tissue in the visible and near-infrared spectral range.

And calculation of scattering and absorption coefficients.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Experimental data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

- CSV
- XLS
- Others

.sdt

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

1

GB

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Other researcher

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No

PTOF Adipose tissue

Photon time-of-flight measurements in the visible and near-infrared spectral range of adipose tissue

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

The photon propagation through adipose tissue in the visible and infrared spectral range.

And calculation of scattering and absorption coefficients.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Experimental data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

- CSV
- XLS
- Others

.sdt

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

1

GB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

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No

PTOF Muscles

Photon time-of-flight measurements in the visible and near-infrared spectral range of muscle tissues

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

The photon propagation through muscle tissue in the visible spectral range.

And calculation of scattering and absorption coefficients.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Experimental data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

- CSV
- XLS
- Others

.sdt

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

1

GB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

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PTOF Brain tissue

Photon time-of-flight measurements in the visible spectral and near-infrared range of brain tissues.

Template: LCS FARP

Type: Dataset

1 Data Summary

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1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

The photon propagation through brain tissue in the visible and near-infrared spectral range.

And calculation of scattering and absorption coefficients.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Experimental data

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- CSV
- XLS
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